

Kanyakumari District during the second season (pishanam). They have long duration and low yield potential. Farmers prefer them because of their high straw yield, the only local feed for cattle.

The performance of TP4121 (CO 25 / CO 40), 163-d duration, was evaluated for 3 yr, 1983-84 to 1985-86 (see table). It had the highest grain yield (5.3 t/ha) in 1984-85; mean grain yield was 4.8 t/ha, 40 and 61% more than Vallarakkan and Valsiramundan,

Performance of TP4121 at ARS Thirupathisaram, Tamil Nadu, India, 1983-84 to 1985-86.

Variety	Parents	Grain yield (t/ha)				Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles (no./hill)	Panicle wt (g)
		1983-84	1984-85	1985-86	Mean				
TP4121	CO 25/CO 40	4.2	5.3	5.0	4.8	163	123.6	9	2.13
CO 25	CO 4/ADT10	2.6	4.2	3.8	3.5	162	122.4	7	2.00
Vallarakkan	Traditional	1.9	4.3	4.0	3.4	180	126.7	7	1.85
Valsiramundan	Traditional	1.7	3.4	3.8	3.0	170	122.9	7	1.98

respectively.

TP4121 is 123 cm tall with short bold white grains. Its higher yield potential is

due mainly to higher panicle weight and increased number of productive tillers. □

BG380-2, a high-yielding, short- to medium-duration rice

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An experiment in the 1986-87 dry season tested 22 International Rice Yield Nursery entries in a random block design with 3 replications. BG380-2

Yield performance of promising entries. Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India, 1986-87.

Entry	Parentage	Grain yield (t/ha)	% of IR20	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)
BG380-2	BG90-2*/OB677	9.4	149.2	90	93.7	23.1	520
BR316-15-4-4-1	IR5 (P)/Biplab	9.3	147.6	86	106.8	21.4	457
S512 B-199	—	7.9	125.4	97	82.4	19.8	540
C1333-4	IR42/C4-63(G)	7.7	122.2	92	65.9	18.2	477
IR20	IR262/TKM6	6.3	—	95	83.9	19.5	493
CD (0.05)		1.9					

yielded 9.4 t/ha in 120 d, compared with 6.3 t/ha in 125 d for IR20 (see table). BG380-2 can replace IR20 — which

showed reduction in yield — for cultivation in the Periyar-Vaigai River Project. □

Performance of selected photoperiod-sensitive breeding lines in Bangladesh

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Bangladesh farmers grow transplant aman (T. aman) rice after aus rice or jute, in a delayed planting. Photoperiod-insensitive varieties are subjected to cold stress at flowering, resulting in drastic yield loss.

Eleven photoperiod-sensitive advanced breeding lines, one local photoperiod-sensitive check, and one long-duration, high-yielding check were evaluated during the 1986 T. aman season at Joydebpur, Comilla, and Barisal. Test entries were evaluated in normal and late plantings. The normal planting was 8 Aug using 30-d-old seedlings, the late planting was in Sep,

Ancillary characteristics of the selected photoperiod-sensitive lines. Bangladesh, 1986 T. aman.

Designation	Parentage	Plant height (cm)		Yield (t/ha)	
		1st	2d	1st	2d
BR716-7-2-1-1	DA29/BR4	115	105	4.2	3.5
BR545-5-1-2-1	BR52-87-1/Tilakkachari	106	95	4.0	3.3
BR1141-2B-37	BR4/Jhingasail	128	112	4.0	3.1
Nizersail (local check)	—	126	110	2.8	2.3
BR11 (check)	IR20/IR5-47-2	110	90	3.8	1.0

using 45-d-old seedlings. Entries were grown in 5.4 m long × 12 row wide plots at 25- × 15-cm spacing with 2 seedlings/ hill, in a randomized complete block design with 3 replications. The whole plot was harvested for yield data, which were statistically analyzed separately for location, planting date, and the combination of locations.

No entry gave high yields at all locations (see table). Combined yield analysis of both plantings showed an interaction between location and variety.

BR716-7-2-1-1, BR545-5-1-2-1, and BR1141-2B-37 were selected for future breeding of photoperiod-sensitive varieties. □

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